

**ENTERPRISING AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP AN IMPERATIVE FOR
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN UNIVERSITIES: A STUDY OF
ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEPARTMENT EBONYI STATE UNIVERSITY
ABAKALIKI**

BY

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Submitted: December 5, 2019.

Abstract

Enterprising and entrepreneurship have gained public interest due to changes in global economy, pressure in labour market demanding graduates to equip themselves with skills to help them prosper and government support to foster enterprising culture to boost economic growth. The analytical technique for test of hypothesis was Analysis of variance (ANOVA) to achieve the set objective 270 respondents answered the question that was asked using questionnaire. Survey method was adopted in methodology. Enterprise and entrepreneurship can provide high learning opportunities best when related to courses chosen by students. A lot of initiatives has been introduced by Nigerian government in schools mostly universities to encourage the spirit of entrepreneurship within our vast population. Numerous opportunities are available for universities when enterprising and entrepreneurship are integrated to restructure learning, building capacity and skill in students which will help reduce pressure in labour market because entrepreneurship is the key to economic development. Recommendations were made; it unleashes students potentials that will lead to wealth creation, job creation, new industries. Conclusion - Government should help by organizing practical training, giving financial assistance, bank loan, also monitoring people to know whether those materials given are utilized effectively to avoid waste.

Keywords – Enterprising, Entrepreneurship, economic development, Job creation

INTRODUCTION

In recent time enterprising and entrepreneurship have taken over events the way things are it will help millions of Nigerians to be self-employed, creating job opportunities for our vast population, creating wealth and reducing much dependant, on government, entrepreneurship all over the world is acclaimed as a significant factor in economic development; it is a varitable change agent in structure of business and society. As a change agent it acts as a catalyst for generation of new ideas, new products, and new methods of production and distribution of products so produced (Ethelmary and Ibiam 2011). Jobs created, new technologies developed, improved production method, increase in output both in terms of quality and quantity are all ingredients for economic development. Enterprising and entrepreneurship play vital role in economic development, it enhances the moral of youth which are mainly found in universities and when caught at this early stage, it will help them grow with it, live with it and innovate it in the way that it will attract the interest of their counterparts in school, which will embrace development Nigeria since independence has been battling to change the face of its economic landscape, colonial masters paid little attention to self employment, they believe mainly in white collar job but many government leaders have come and gone with unemployment being on the increase and population on the increase too, they now know there is a serious cause for alarm, thereby indicating a missing link in our development strategies, that missing link is entrepreneurial consciousness. Entrepreneurs are people shackle says that is creative, imaginative and original, perceives business opportunities, they create and imagine opportunities. Casson sees entrepreneurs as people that have command over resources, they coordinate scarce resources and take decisions.

Entrepreneurship as a process by which economic and commercial activities necessary for improvement of standard of living of society are created. These are created by entrepreneurs, individuals, institutions, corporations and government (Udu and Eze, 2008). Enterprising-energetic and progressive displaying bravery and daring in the attempt of task. In recognition of uncounted contribution of enterprising and entrepreneurship to economic development, by

government, they have made several attempts. As (Agbonifa et al, 1999) assert that government has developed assistance programmes for industrial, economic and commercial development of the country, introducing it as a main course in tertiary institutions, encouraging training even abroad, workshop etc. Many debates have been ongoing on contribution of enterprising and entrepreneurship to economic development, they serve as a vehicle for propagation and diffusion of innovative ideas of far reaching dimensions contributing to labour stability in those sectors, transformation of industries, ability to mobilize finance, resources utilization, facilities conversion. (Udu and Eze, 2008) identified entrepreneurship contribution as bridging the gap between science and market place, creation of new technology, creation of new enterprise, creation of job opportunities, structural; change in business and society. Enterprising and entrepreneurship have grown into fascinating and interesting field of study worldwide. The foundation of growth of economics of most developed countries is entrepreneurship and for it to take root in universities all hands must be on deck.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The rate of failure of entrepreneurship activities in the country is alarming Nigeria is one of the most populated countries in the whole world; unemployment is on the high side, students graduating every year joining the counterparts in the cue. The problem of this study indicates inadequate infrastructure to support entrepreneurship, limited financing, insecurity, lack of training and vocational facilities, road network, power failure which have led to closure and some recording huge losses in operation.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The general objective of the study is to determine the effect of enterprising and entrepreneurship in economic development in universities. The specific objectives include:

- i. To ascertain the extent to which enterprising and entrepreneurship will lead to variety of job creation.

- ii. To examine the extent to which enterprising and entrepreneurship will lead to decrease in unemployment.
- iii. To determine to what extent will enterprising and entrepreneurship lead to wealth creation in economic development.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Based on the objectives the following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

Ho – Enterprising and entrepreneurship does not affect wealth creation in economic development

Ho - Enterprising and entrepreneurship does not affect decrease of unemployment

Ho - Enterprising and entrepreneurship does not affect variety of job opportunity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Enterprising is having the attitude, initiative and ability to recognize opportunities and confidence to make the most of them. We can also see it in this way finding new idea or solution to old problems, discovering a more resourceful way of tackling a challenge, organizing an event or having the vision to start a new society or service. Volunteering or getting involved in community project and employers value enterprising people for fresh thinking they bring to workplace.

Entrepreneurial – This involves using skills to bring that new business idea, venture, product or service to life, also being prepared to take risk in order to achieve success.

Employable – Having the skill, knowledge and personal attributes to catch the eyes of employers. It means understanding how to be effective in the workplace and successful in your chosen career, for the benefit of yourself, your colleagues, the community and wider economy.

As a graduate you will not only be highly employable but also Enterprising and Entrepreneurial. We call them the three Es Life Skills

Entrepreneurship is a process of creating something new with value by devoting the necessary time and efforts, assuming and accompanying financial, psychic and social risks

and receiving the rewards of monetary and personal satisfactions and independence. (Histich and Peters, 1998) while (odusina, 2011) perceives entrepreneurship as a process of using available capital in any form for business endeavours in an open and free market endeavours in an open and free market economy for the sole purpose of making profit.

(Udu et al, 2000) believe those entrepreneurs are agents of change, creating chaos by disrupting the status quo in constructive ways to instigate new products, processes or knowledge. This theory is the basis upon which it is asserted that innovation is the hallmark of entrepreneurship. On this corridor's principle applies to entrepreneur because by doing one thing or following one idea, new opportunities arises from these efforts and subsequent opportunities may arise from continued efforts and this leads to practice makes perfect. There is need for entrepreneurship because of unemployment and poverty rate in our country Nigeria. Nwangwu 2007 opined that failure of tertiary institution to embrace the spirit of entrepreneurship to students is one of the problems of unemployment because students should be equipped with skills with which to exploit the natural resources that abound in Nigeria. All these factors have rendered the pursuit of self-reliance among our graduates difficult to attain. Entrepreneurship is a key driver of economy.

BENEFITS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP TO UNDERGRADUATES

(Udu et al, 2008), entrepreneurship bridges gap between science and market place, creation of new technology, creation of new enterprise, creation of job opportunities, and provision of resources. It is also a structural change in business and society.

- Enobong et al (2013)
- Demonstrate skills in business setup
- Demonstrate skills in maintaining business
- Ability to find next level of training or access to other resources and services
- Demonstrate business management/operation skill
- Use components of business plan
- Determine impact of unemployment
- See entrepreneurship as a means of living

- Problem solving, being creative
- Self awareness, self worth, ability to control.

Joseph Schumpeter an economist in his theory describes entrepreneurship as “Creative destruction” because an entrepreneur takes some new ideas and new combinations to render ideas from past obsolete. It is quest for change, entertaining new ideas and responding to them, to convert these changes into new opportunities that entrepreneurship concerns itself with.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Newton P. 2017 investigated Entrepreneurship and wealth creation using 10 SME’s in Ghana, descriptive survey design was adopted as method of the study and questionnaire were formulated to gather data, correlation was also used in testing the hypotheses, it was found that entrepreneurship has great relationship in wealth creation as they are known for economic development entrepreneurship also aid in wealth creation.

Abdulashi .S. carried out a research in university of jos using department of Entrepreneurship to determine the relationship between entrepreneurship and job opportunity. Descriptive survey design was adopted, questionnaire used in gathering the data, regression analysis applied and it was found out that there is great relationship between entrepreneurship and job opportunity because in the department of entrepreneurship small scale businesses are put into practice which can sustain students when they leave the university with it they can be self employed and can even employ people into the business.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research method adopted in this study is survey method. Survey method is probably the best method available to a researcher who is interested in collecting original data. Survey method (Ezeani, 1998) is the collected factual information that describes the existing phenomena. The survey method is preferred to other methods because the same set of

questions will be directed to all respondents in the sample in order to find their opinions on the subject matter.

AREA OF THE STUDY

The study will concentrate in Ebonyi State University Abakaliki (Entrepreneurship Department).

POPULATION AND SAMPLE SIZE OF THE STUDY

By the nature of the research title, it concerns enterprising and entrepreneurship an imperative for economic development. The study will use quasi experimental design and primary data no need for sample size determination. The entire population will be used because population is not up to 1000, the entire students in the department numbering 270 as at June 2019 as extracted from faculty office.

Table 1: Population of students in entrepreneurship department

Students	Level	Location	Population
	Year 4	Igbariam	84
	Year 3		66
	Year 2		75
	Year 1		45
	Total		270

Source: Extracted from each of the faculty office at Igbariam campus as at June 2019.

SOURCE OF DATA

Primary source of data will be employed. These data will be sourced as first-hand information and remain in raw form as no researcher has made use of them. The instrument of sourcing/collecting primary data will be standardized questionnaire test though data will come in both quantitative and quantitative forms.

DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

In this study, the descriptive statistics such frequency counts with simple percentage were used to analyse the four research questions. At the inferential level of analyses, Linear regression was used to test hypotheses 2, 3 and 4 while Hypothesis 1 was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient to determine the extent of correlation between x and y variables (Independent and Dependent). All analyses were done through the application of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 20.00 windows).

The formulae are:

Regression Equation $(y) = a + bx$

Slope $(b) = (N\Sigma XY - (\Sigma X)(\Sigma Y)) / (N\Sigma X^2 - (\Sigma X)^2)$

Intercept $(a) = (\Sigma Y - b(\Sigma X)) / N$

x and y are the variables.

b = The slope of the regression line

a = The intercept point of the regression line and the y axis.

N = Number of values or elements

X = First Score

Y = Second Score

ΣXY = Sum of the product of first and Second Scores

ΣX = Sum of First Scores

ΣY = Sum of Second Scores

ΣX^2 = Sum of square First Scores

Pearson product moment correlation coefficient for sample data is denoted by

"r". The formula for Pearson correlation coefficient r is given by

Where,
$$r = \frac{n(\Sigma Xy) - (\Sigma X)(\Sigma Y)}{\sqrt{n\Sigma X^2 - (\Sigma X)^2 \quad n\Sigma Y - (\Sigma Y)^2}}$$

Where,

r = Pearson correlation coefficient

x = Values in first set of data

y = Values in second set of data

n = Total number of value

Decision Rule

In testing hypotheses, the calculated value of the test statistic was compared with critical or table value of the statistic. The critical or table value serves as a benchmark for rejecting or not rejecting the null hypotheses. Therefore, the decision rule applied in this research was to reject the null hypotheses if the calculated value at 5% significance level with respective degrees of freedom is greater than the table value, otherwise do not reject.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics enterprising entrepreneurship and increase in sales volume.

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Enterprising and entrepreneurship	1.8261	1.16043	958
Increase in sales volume	1.9065	1.26713	958

Table 4.2 Correlations of work experience and customer satisfaction

		work experience	customer satisfaction
enterprising entrepreneurship	Pearson Correlation	1	.955"
			.000
	N	958	958
Increase in sale volume	Pearson Correlation	.955"	1
		.000	
	N	958	958

Source: SPSS Version 20.00.

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the enterprising entrepreneurship via, increase in sales volume. with a mean response of 1.8261 and std. deviation of 1.16043 for enterprising entrepreneurship and a mean response of 1.9065 and std. deviation of 1.26713 , increase in

sales volume and number of respondents (958). By careful observation of standard deviation values, there is not much difference in terms of the standard deviation scores. This implies that there is about the same variability of data points between the dependent and independent variables.

Table 4.3 is the Pearson correlation coefficient for enterprising entrepreneurship and increase in sales volume. The correlation coefficient shows 0.955. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there is a significant positive relationship between enterprising and entrepreneurship and, increase in sales volume ($r = .955$).

The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 956 degrees of freedom ($df. = n-2$) at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .955, p < .05$). However, since the computed $r = .955$, is greater than the table value of $.195$ we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a positive relationship between enterprising entrepreneurship and increase in sales volume ($r = .955, P < .05$).

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Enterprising and entrepreneurship will not lead to decrease in unemployment

H1: enterprising and entrepreneurship will lead to decrease in unemployment

Table 4.3 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Enterprising entrepreneurship	1.8182	1.09298	958
Unemployment	1.6621	1.01787	958

Table 4.4 Correlations

		Enterprising Entrepreneurship	Unemployment
Pearson Correlation	Enterprising entrepreneurship	1.000	.619
	Unemployment	.619	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Enterprising entrepreneurship		.000
	Unemployment	.000	
N	Enterprising entrepreneurship	958	958
	Unemployment	958	958

Table 4.5 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the	Durbin-Watson
1	.619 ^a	.383	.382	.85904	.054

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enterprising entrepreneurship

b. Dependent Variable: unemployment

b. Dependent Variable: unemployment

Table 4.5 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	231.342	1	231.342	313.489	.000 ^a
	Residual	371.931	956	.738		
	Total	603.273	957			

a. Predictors: (Constant), enterprising

Entrepreneurship b. Dependent Variable:

unemployment

Table 4.6 Coefficients³

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
			Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.713	.073		9.744	.000
	Training	.665	.038	.619	17.706	.000

a. Dependent Variable: unemployment

R = 0.619

R² = 0.383

F = 313.489

T = 9.744

DW = 0.054

b. Interpretation:

The regression sum of squares (231.342) is less than the residual sum of squares (371.931), which indicates that more of the variation in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistics (0.000) is less than 0.05, which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance. R, the correlation coefficient which has a value of 0.619, indicates that there is positive relationship between enterprising entrepreneurship and unemployment. R square, the coefficient of determination, shows that 38.3% of the variation in the unemployment is explained by the model.

With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .85904. The Durbin Watson statistics of 0.054, which is not more than 2, indicates there is no auto correlation. Unemployment coefficient of 0.619, indicates a positive significance between enterprising entrepreneurship and unemployment, which is statistically significant (with t = 9.744). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Thus enterprising entrepreneurship has a significant effect on unemployment

Hypothesis Three

Ho: Enterprising and entrepreneurship does not lead to wealth creation in economic development

H1: Enterprising and entrepreneurship lead to wealth creation in economic development

Table 4.8 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Enterprising entrepreneurship	3.3192	1.62412	958
Wealth Creation	2.7173	1.54910	958

Table 4.9 Correlations

		service delivery	organizational culture
Pearson Correlation	Enterprising entrepreneurship	1.000	.906
	Wealth Creation Talent management	.906	1.000
Sig. (Mailed)	Enterprising entrepreneurship		.000
	Wealth Creation	.000	
N	Enterprising entrepreneurship	958	958
	Wealth Creation	958	958

Table 4.10 Model Summary¹

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.906 ^a	.821	.820	.68838	.031

a. Predictors: (Constant), Wealth Creation b. Dependent Variable: service delivery.

Table 4.11 ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1123.548	1	1123.548	2.371E3	.000 ^a
	Residual	245.460	956	.474		
	Total	1369.008	957			

a. Predictors: (Constant), enterprise entrepreneurship. Dependent Variable: Wealth Creation

Table 4.12 Coefficients³

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.738	.061		12.104	.000
	Talent management	.950	.020	.906	48.693	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Wealth Creation

R - 0.906 =

R² 0.821 =

F T 2.371E3 -

D 12.149 =

W 0.031

Interpretation:

The regression sum of squares (1123.548) is greater than the residual sum of squares (245.460), which indicates that more of the variation in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistics (0.000) is less than 0.05, which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance.

R, the correlation coefficient which has a value of 0.906, indicates that there is positive relationship between enterprising entrepreneurship and wealth creation in economic development. R square, the coefficient of determination, shows that 61.1% of the variation in the innovation is explained by the model.

With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .68838. The Durbin Watson statistics of 0.031, which is not more than 2, indicates there is no autocorrelation.

Enterprising entrepreneurship coefficient of 0.782 indicates a positive significance between enterprising entrepreneurship and wealth creation in economic development, which is statistically significant (with $t=12.149$). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. That enterprising entrepreneurship significantly affects wealth creation in economic development

R = 0.619

R² = 0.383

F = 313.489

T = 9.744

DW = 0.054

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FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The result based on the descriptive statistics reveals the following:

1. That there is a positive relationship between enterprising entrepreneurship and increase in sales volume
2. That enterprising entrepreneurship has a significant effect on unemployment
3. That enterprising entrepreneurship significantly affects wealth creation in economic development

CONCLUSION

The level of economic development and quality of life in the society is determined by enterprising and entrepreneurship. The factor that determines the quality and quantity of goods and services in a society can produce at any point in time is the level of entrepreneurship development in that society enterprising and entrepreneurship describes the behaviours of profit seeking individuals and institutions who organize other factors of productions having in mind of producing goods for profit. Enterprising and entrepreneurship are so importance that every tertiary institution must incorporate in their curriculum in other to produce large number of entrepreneurship minded individuals as done by Ebonyi State University Abakaliki.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- All the tertiary institutions in Nigeria will inculcate enterprising and entrepreneurship in their curriculum to help increase domestic product in the country.
- Government should give attention to enterprising and entrepreneurship development in the country to help decrease unemployment.
- Government should also provide good economic environment that will lead to variety of job opportunities that will help graduates attach themselves to something after graduation.
- Government and society should identify students and individuals with entrepreneurial traits, motivate and develop their own small and medium scale business enterprises (SMES) which will lead to economic development and wealth creation in the society.

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